

Hybrid Workshop – 22 November 2023 (14:00 – 18:00 CET)

Location: IRENA Innovation and Technology Centre, Bonn, Germany

IRENA and IEECP Joint Workshop:

Stakeholder-driven energy scenarios for a just transition: *Dialogue with the scientific community*

Participatory processes are essential components of long-term energy scenario development. These processes require collaborative engagements that gather insights from government officials, experts, citizens, electricity market participants, and industry. Involving a wide range of stakeholders in scenario building and energy modeling has the potential to enrich the quality and viability of proposed energy scenarios, build trust, and manage risks, while fostering collaboration. At the same time, stakeholder engagement can enable a debate on envisioned energy futures and the different trade-offs. This can lead to the formulation of widely accepted energy strategies that will drive a successful energy transition.

IRENA's Long-term Energy Scenarios (LTES) Network has organized several activities centered around participatory processes. These include a session titled "Stakeholder Engagement for an Inclusive LTES Development Process" at the [2nd International Forum on LTES](#), a lunch session on "Energy scenario communication for strengthened inputs and trustworthy outputs" at the [IEW 2022](#), a workshop focused on participatory processes for developing national long-term energy scenarios at the [4th International Forum on LTES](#), and an online workshop in July 2023 that facilitated knowledge sharing among government scenario practitioners on the objectives, challenges, and benefits of involving diverse stakeholders in the development of long-term energy scenarios. Findings from these activities will be used to formulate a toolkit for energy planners to support developing stakeholder engagement processes.

With the support of the Horizon Europe-funded [European SSH center](#), scientists from the Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy (IEECP), TU Delft (Netherlands), University College London (United Kingdom) and ΔE+ Research Lab, among others, are currently leading a debate on the relevance of interdisciplinary research and participatory energy modeling for just energy transitions. The results will be published in a book chapter edited by the SSH center to strengthen European energy policy.

In this context, a workshop co-organized by IRENA and IEECP will bring together the scientific community, modelers in governmental institutions, and other energy and climate actors to discuss the importance of developing more participatory scenarios for a more inclusive and just transition, as well as the possibilities of involving the wider and interdisciplinary scientific community in national energy scenario planning.

Objective:

- Share case studies and best practices for effective stakeholder engagement conducted by the scientific community and energy agencies.
- Facilitate the exchange and discussion of barriers and lessons learned for interdisciplinary engagement in technical energy system modelling processes.
- Discuss the limited ability of models to integrate social and political transition aspects, and how stakeholder exchanges could potentially address this gap

- Discuss how modeling processes can lead to more inclusive and just scenarios

Outcome:

- The insights and experiences shared by participants will contribute to the development of a comprehensive toolkit for scenario practitioners.
- The perspectives on justice and energy modeling will contribute to a book chapter on the role of energy modeling in informing debates on just energy transitions.

Guiding questions for the discussions:

- How are energy scenarios and modeling tools used to inform policy decisions?
- What are best practices for meaningfully engaging stakeholders in modeling processes?
- What are the gaps in energy models to inform just energy transitions?
- How should energy scenarios and models be improved to better contribute to policy debates?

Registration link: [CLICK HERE](#)

Tentative agenda:

Time	Description and speakers	Segment
14:00	Snacks, coffee, and tour de table	Offline only
15:00	Welcome by IRENA and IEECP	Hybrid
15:10	<p>Setting the scene: Rethinking energy scenario processes: inclusive pathways to climate neutrality</p> <p>Presentation: Connor McGookin, Energy Policy & Modelling Group, MaREI Centre, University College Cork, Ireland & ΔE+ Research Lab, Simon Fraser University, Canada</p> <p>Q&A</p>	Hybrid
15:30	<p>Lightning talks session*: Best practices for meaningful stakeholder engagement in scenario building and modeling processes. <i>[to distinguish between activities carried out by scientists and national processes involving scientists]</i></p>	Hybrid
16:45	<p>Interactive debate with the audience: Improving energy modeling tools and scenario building processes to better support just transition policy decisions</p>	Hybrid
17:50	Next steps	Hybrid
18:00	Snacks and networking	Offline only

*If you would like to prepare a 2-3 minute intervention about your experience with participatory modelling and the importance of scientific insights within the process, please reach out to Diana Süsser at diana@ieecp.org or Nadeem Goussous at ngoussous@irena.org.